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**Jambolan as remediable in stabilizing proper function of testis of alloxan instigated
male *Mus musculus***

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Focus of research was to explore the efficacy of *Syzigium cumuni* (jamun) seeds in amelioration of histoarchitecture of reproductive organ i.e. testis in hyperglycemic mice, besides various Indian herbal plants with proven antihyperglycemic properties in amelioration of hyperglycemia. These include babul (*Acacia Arabica*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), gurhal (*Hibiscus rosa-sinesis*), bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia*), giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*), methi (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*). Diabetes affects the normal levels of blood glucose metabolism and any shift in values of such parameters become essential tool for stabilising magnitude of hyperglycemia. In diabetes glucose level increases significantly and if condition persists for a longer time, then referred to as hyperglycemia. Stipulated doses of Alloxan monohydrate were injected into mice, leading to destitution in insulin secretion and ultimately leading to hyperglycemic condition in mice. They were then fed with *Syzigium cumuni* (jamun) seed powder along with food for three weeks (Group III). HE stained sections of Testis of alloxan monohydrate induced diabetic (Group–II) and that of *Syzigium cumuni* (jamun) seed powder fed were compared. Diabetic (Group–II) animals showed severe damages in normal histological architecture. Cytoplasmic vacuolization, cellular infiltration of acute inflammatory cells were seen in diabetic mice and is found to be pronounced with increased exposure period of 21 days. But in case of (Group–III) animals HE stained sections of Testis cells were found to be recovered. *Syzigium cumuni* seed powder acts to attenuate degenerative changes in testis. Gradual enhancements in damages in normal histological architecture of testis in diabetic mice was controlled by supplementary doses of *Syzigium cumuni* (jamun) seed powder along with food. Seeds contain alkaloid, jambosine, and glycoside jambolin or antimellin, which halts diastatic conversion of starch into sugar (Akbar 2020) and stimulates the secretion of pancreatic insulin and it also restores architecture of pancreatic β -cells in diabetic experimental animal cells (Sharma et al., 2011; Sharma et al., 2008). Therefore, *Syzigium cumuni* seed powder as alternative approaches are eagerly needed, such as plant-

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based therapies attract much interest as they are effective in reducing reproductive complications in the Diabetic patients, and who are resistant or intolerant to conventional pharmacotherapy.